

Studies in Quinoline Compounds. Part II. Some Derivatives of 4-Phenyl-2-methylquinoline.

By UPENDRA NATH BRAHMACHARI AND TARAPADA BHATTACHARYA.

The enhanced toxicity of 4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline towards certain kinds of protozoa when compared with that of quinoline and quinaldine induced us to synthesise a few derivatives of this important compound. Up till now only very few compounds of this series have been synthesised. In the synthesis of these compounds we have taken the help of the reaction of Doebner and v. Miller modified by Beyer (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1886, ii, 33, 399). In this way we have obtained

- (i) 6-nitro-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline,
- (ii) 8-nitro-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline, and a few derivatives of them.

By heating *p*- and *o*-nitroanilines respectively with benzoylacetone, little or no condensation takes place. Similarly on heating *p*-nitroaniline hydrochloride with a mixture of paraldehyde and acetophenone, already saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas, very little or scarcely any, condensation takes place. But by certain modifications of the latter method to be described below we have ultimately succeeded in getting the above condensation products, and the increased basic properties of these substances enabled us in separating them from their parent substances.

These nitro-compounds are of a very pale yellowish green colour. They readily dissolve in dilute acids. Stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid easily reduce them to the corresponding amines which can be separated through their finely crystalline stannichlorides. They also react, rather easily, with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde to give the corresponding styryl compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Nitro-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline.

A mixture of acetophenone (50 c.c.) and paraldehyde (80 c.c.) is cooled in ice and saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas. This

mixture is then allowed to stand for 48 hours. It is then again saturated in cold with dry hydrochloric acid gas and allowed to stand for 24 hours more. This is now slowly added to an intimate mixture of *p*-nitroaniline (58 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (90 c.c.) and the whole heated for 5 to 6 hours on a water-bath with occasional shaking. It is then largely diluted with water and the supernatant liquid carefully filtered through a coarse filter paper. The clear filtrate is then cooled by adding ice. A strong aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide is then cautiously added to precipitate nearly the whole of the unreacted *p*-nitroaniline. It is then filtered and the filtrate supersaturated with alkali. The required nitrophenyl-2-methylquinoline thus precipitated, is separated by filtration, washed with water and dried on a porous plate. Under this condition it has a fine greenish colour. It can be further purified by recrystallisation from a mixture of acetone and ether.

The pure compound, m.p. 141°, possesses a yellowish-green colour. It gives precipitates with potassium dichromate, phosphomolybdic acid and picric acid, dissolves very easily in alcohol and acetone and moderately in ether and in boiling water. The solution of the compound in dilute mineral acids possesses an orange-yellow colour. (Found: N, 11.1. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.6 per cent.).

6-Amino-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline

The above nitro-compound can be conveniently reduced as follows. To a mixture of stannous chloride (30 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) the nitro-compound (6.5 g.) is gradually added under constant shaking. If the mixture gets very hot, it must be cooled under the tap. On cooling the fine crystalline stannichloride of the amine crystallises out. It is filtered, washed with concentrated hydrochloric acid and dissolved in about 200 c.c. of boiling water. The tin is precipitated as sulphide and removed by filtration. The filtrate when made alkaline with dilute sodium hydroxide precipitates the amine as fine needles. It is then recrystallised from ether; m. p. 188°. It can be diazotised and coupled with β -naphthol. The solution of the substance in acetone possesses a beautiful violet-blue fluorescence. (Found: N, 12.3. $C_{16}H_{14}N_2$ requires N, 12.0 per cent.).

6-Nitro-4-phenyl-2-p-dimethylaminostyrylquinoline.

This compound can be easily prepared by heating to gentle boiling over a small flame, a mixture of 6-nitro-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in equimolecular proportions for about 10 to 15 minutes. The product is then poured into water. The solid thus separated is then purified by recrystallisation from acetone. It has a brownish-red colour and melts at 64°. (Found: N, 10·8. $C_{25}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 10·6 per cent.).

8-Nitro-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline.

A mixture of acetophenone (50 g.) and paraldehyde (30 g.) is saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas as described before. This is then added to a mixture of *o*-nitroaniline (58 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (90 g.) and the whole heated on a water-bath for 7 to 8 hours. The product is then largely diluted (to about 2 litres) and, after filtration through a coarse filter paper, the filtrate is made strongly alkaline with sodium hydroxide. The *o*-nitroaniline remains in solution while the 8-nitro-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline precipitates out as a greenish-black pasty mass. It is then dried on a porous plate and recrystallised from acetone. The compound looks pale yellowish-green; m. p. 94°. In its other behaviour it resembles the corresponding 6-nitro-compound. (Found: N, 10·9. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10·6 per cent.).

8-Amino-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline.

The above nitro-compound can also be reduced very easily by stannous chloride just as in the previous case. The filtrate, after the separation of tin sulphide, is evaporated on a water-bath when the amine hydrochloride remains behind. It is very difficult to get the free amine from this hydrochloride. The hydrochloride possesses an yellow colour and begins to decompose above 210°. It dissolves very easily in water to give an orange-yellow solution. (Found: N, 10·7. $C_{16}H_{13}N_2Cl$ requires N, 10·3 per cent.).

8-Nitro-4-phenyl-2-p-dimethylaminostyrylquinoline.

The preparation and purification of this compound is exactly similar to those of the corresponding 6-nitro-compound, 8-nitro-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline being substituted for the 6-nitro-4-phenyl-2-methylquinoline. It melts at 129°. (Found: N, 10.9. $C_{25}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 10.6 per cent.)

THE BRAHMACHARI RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
82-3, CORNWALLIS STREET, CALCUTTA.

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